

Polycyclic Compounds. Part III. Derivatives of β -Tetralone

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5-Methyl-2-tetralone (I) from commercially available 6-methoxy-1-tetralone (II) in a pure state has been prepared. Alkylation¹ of β -tetralone (III) with the methiodide of 1-diethylamino-5-methyl-3-oxohexane (IV) has also been studied.

To the methiodide of 1-diethylamino-5-methyl-3-oxohexane (IV), prepared in the reaction vessel, a benzene solution of β -tetralone (III) was added and the reaction was initiated by addition of an ethanolic solution of potassium ethoxide. Under such a mild condition, the chief product in the present instance was 1-(5'-methyl-3'-oxohexyl)-2-tetralone(VI). Further experiments are necessary to prepare (V) by prolonged heating with the basic catalyst².

(I)

(II)

(III)

(IV)

(V)

5-Methyl-2-tetralone (I) was prepared from 6-methoxy-1-tetralone (II) through the Grignard synthesis³ with methylmagnesium iodide, followed by dehydrogenation⁴ with sulphur and reduction⁵ of the naphthalene derivative (VIII), so formed, with sodium and ethanol and purified through the bisulphite.

1. Robinson and Cornforth, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 1861; Akter *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1959, 4058.
2. Adamson *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1937, 1576.
3. Bachmann, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1938, 3, 434.
4. Ruzicka, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1922, 5, 345.
4. Cf. "Org. Syntheses", Vol 32, p. 97; Robinson *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 690.

There are two reactive centres of β -tetralones. Formylation and oxalation occur at 3-position⁶, but the alkylation of β tetralone with ketonic Mannich bases at 1-position is reminiscent of many such compounds⁷.

EXPERIMENTAL

1-*Methyl-6-methoxy-3,4-dihydronaphthalene* (VII).—To a Grignard reagent, prepared from magnesium (9 g.), methyl iodide (27 ml), and dry ether (200 ml), was added with stirring a solution of 6-methoxy-1-tetralone (II) (50 g.) in dry benzene (100 ml), diluted with dry ether (50 ml). After 12 hr. at the room temperature, the mixture was gently refluxed for 1 hr. It was then cooled and decomposed with H_2SO_4 (cold, conc., 21 ml). The ether-benzene layer was separated, washed with water, dried (Na_2SO_4), and evaporated. The residue was distilled to provide (VII) (39 g.), b.p. 128-30°/6 mm. (Found: C, 82.70; H, 8.08. $C_{12}H_{14}O$ requires C, 82.75; H, 8.04%).

1-*Methyl-6-methoxynaphthalene* (VIII).—The preceding compound (39 g.) was heated with sulphur (7.2 g.) on a nitre bath (220-40°) for 3 hr. The residue was distilled to provide the hydrocarbon (VIII) (35.2 g.), b.p. 145-48°/6 mm. (Found: C, 83.76; H, 7.00. $C_{12}H_{12}O$ requires C, 83.72; H, 6.97%).

5-*Methyl-2-tetralone* (I).—Sodium (16g.), cut into small pieces, was added during 7-8 min. to a solution of 1-methyl-6-methoxynaphthalene (15.4 g.) in boiling ethanol (142 ml) (bath 115°). Ethanol (30 ml) was further added and heating continued under reflux till the metal had disappeared (40 min.). Water (50 ml) was cautiously added to the reaction mixture and most of the ethanol (125 ml) removed under diminished pressure. The residue was mixed with more water (25 ml) and treated with HCl (conc., 75 ml) till acidic to Congo red. This liquid was then boiled on a steam bath for another $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. The residue was cooled, extracted with ether, and the extract shaken with sodium metabisulphite (30 g.) in water (45 ml). The bisulphite compound (26.9 g.) was filtered, washed with ether, and dried (air). The suspension of the bisulphite (52 g.) in ether (100 ml) was treated with sodium carbonate (100 g.) in water (240 ml) slowly with occasional shaking till it completely went into solution. The ether extract was separated and the solvent removed. The residue on distillation furnished the compound (I) as a colorless liquid (17.6 g.) b.p. 134-35°/6 mm. (Found: C, 82.50; H, 7.53. $C_{11}H_{12}O$ requires C, 82.50; H, 7.50%).

6. Soffer *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 1556; Pelletier and Parthasarathy, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1964, No. 2, 103; Pelletier *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1965, No. 1, 41; Grafen and Turner, *ibid.*, 1964, No. 52, 3935.
7. Crowley and Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 2001; Cornforth and Robinson, *ibid.*, 1946, 676; Grob and Jundt, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1952, **35**, 2111; Pike and Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 3348; Johnson *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **82**, 3400.

1-(5'-Methyl-3'-oxohexyl)-2-tetralone (VI).—A solution of β -tetralone (7.3 g.) in dry benzene (50 ml) was added to the methiodide of 1-diethylamino-5-methyl-3-oxohexane (IV), prepared from amino-ketone (9.25 g.) and methyl iodide (3.55 ml). An ethanolic solution of potassium ethoxide from potassium (3.25 g.) and anhydrous ethanol (50 ml) was then added to it. After 12 hr. at the room temperature, the mixture was gently refluxed on a water bath for 1 hr. It was then cooled and decomposed with 2*N*-H₂SO₄ (5.4 ml). The mixture was diluted with water and the oil separating was taken in ether. The aqueous phase was once extracted with ether. The combined ether extracts were washed with water, dried (CaCl₂), and evaporated. The residue on distillation provided a viscous oil (7.1 g.), b.p. 175-80°/6 mm. (Found: C, 79.00; H, 8.60. C₁₇H₂₂O₂ requires C, 79.07, H, 8.52%).

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